

CONTEMPORARY EDUCATIONAL EXPECTATIONS TO ADDRESS LEARNING CONTINUITY IN ARALING PANLIPUNAN

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ABSTRACT

The world was hit by a pandemic causing closure of schools. For learning to continue, there is a shift from face-to-face to distance learning. In this matter, there is a need to explore on the variables that addresses learning continuity in this contemporary times. This study aimed to determine the relationship between educational expectations, learning delivery modality and addressing learning continuity. It also sought to answer which variables of educational expectations and learning delivery modality significantly addressed the learning continuity variables. The data collected from the respondents were analysed using mean, standard deviation, Pearson r, and stepwise multiple linear regression. The results shows that the respondents agree and expected that the educational expectation variables and learning delivery modality significantly addressed the learning continuity variables. A significant positive correlation between educational expectations and addressing learning continuity is established. Learning delivery modality variables has a significant relationship in addressing learning continuity. Furthermore, teachers' instructional practices and expectations in education and online learning significantly addressed the communications and assessment of learning continuity. In addition, learning materials of learning continuity is significantly addressed by online learning, students' academic self-concept and teachers' instructional practices and expectations in education. This study concluded that educational expectations and learning delivery modality addresses learning continuity in the new normal.

Keywords: (a) Education and Teaching; (b) Contemporary Educational Expectations; Learning Delivery Modality; Addressing Learning Continuity in the New Normal; (c) Descriptive Research; Survey Questionnaire; (d) Philippines, Asia